

EMPLOYER BRANDING INTERNALLY: STRATEGY TOWARD INCREASING ORGANIZATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS AND TALENT RETENTION

Kamlesh Kumar Maurya*

* Research Scholar, Personnel Management & Industrial Relations, Dept of Psychology, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

Dr. Manisha Agarwal **

** Professor, Dept. of Psychology, BHU, Varanasi

Abstract:

Purpose – It has been observed by the extensive literature review and through observing new work trends that the employer branding concept has an emphasis on employees' attitudes and behaviors in respect of choosing the organization or to continue with the same with positivity. Talent acquisition practitioners now a day's starts believing on the talent development apart from talent attraction which given rise to internal branding of employer branding, which argue for a wider range of alignment between the employees' values and those of the brand employer. However, very few studies have attempted to provide a platform by which the talent within the organization will be developed and keep them in continuous basis in relationship of employer branding. This paper therefore seeks to explore and demonstrate how the concept of internal branding is interrelated with talent retention and further to demonstrate its role in organizational competitiveness.

Methodology/approach – Literatures incorporating (corporate branding, internal branding, talent management, human resource management and employee retention) were selected for review and examination in terms of their implications for the proposed framework i.e. internal branding will affect talent retention, performance and satisfaction.

Findings – The review of the literature explores and highlights the importance of employer branding and internal branding specially, and it's potential to support the talent acquisition. The analysis of the literature reveals important integration between employer branding internally with the different aspects of human resource management and talent management. Along with the definition this study also facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the implications of the concepts for branding and internal brand management.

Keywords- Employer branding, Internal brand management, Employees attitudes, Employee retention.

Paper type- Conceptual paper

Introduction:

All around the world every organization in spite of their size, type and location are trying and always in quest, to hire talent, who can be an asset for the organization. Everywhere the "War of talent" is going on, but besides this objective it is very crucial to know the right effort to achieve the final objective which is not limited to attraction of talent only, even more, and in short is the "Positive involvement of talent along with trusted relationship even in bad time". In accordance to fulfill the above distinctive objective and to win the war of talent, the one and

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only strategy is to become “Employer of Choice” specifically it may be defined as the “Positive psychological experience of the stakeholders about any organization to join and withhold the positive affiliation with it willingly”.

If we consider the root of the term employer branding it basically originated from the marketing principle and focus is on considering customers. In this respect employer advocates that a brand provides two benefits: differentiation, so that the customer decide more than price and a franchise (Davies, 1992), the next one is an outcome from customer satisfaction with the brand and loyalty to it. Customers choose to purchase for rational reasons but their emotional attachment is also important. Organizational practitioners trying and this research paper is focus to discover the application of these observed effect of branding for internal customers i.e. employees. By framing more people oriented policies, practices, culture, leadership and supportive attitude for employee development organizations achieved remarkable differences in productivity, loyalty, responsibility and finally a healthy work force in continuation. These attributes of a brand – the ability to differentiate, to create loyalty, to satisfy and to develop an emotional attachment are immediate reaction to the employer brand. Since these attributes are intangible and difficult to copy, organizations become sincere about this and showing and relying on human resources managers for more benefits from employer branding. In the words of Balmer and Gray (2003) a strong, favorable corporate brand is a powerful “navigational tool” to a variety of stakeholders, which is not limited to existing employees and shareholders only, but for potential employees as well. Here it come the role of HR to balance the effective corporate brand management which means external orientation with an internal orientation. Thus in conclusion employer branding is the understanding and practical application of the principles to create, maintain and position of a unique image of the company as an employer in the labor market, which is attractive for both potential and current employees, which could give an opportunity for a company to operate successfully under the global competitive conditions.

The findings of Hale (1998) clearly tells the importance of the issue, which demonstrate that 86% of employers have problem in attracting new employees and 58% have experienced difficulty in retaining their employees. The cost of employee turnover can be evaluated immediately but its effects cannot be stabilized with the pace of organization productivity which adversely affect on the competitive ability of the organization. Since turnover has observed and hidden losses with it, it is very important to deal with it timely with innovative practices. Therefore stable strategy to overcome this continuous problem for many sectors for example the IT, BPO, Retail and so on is required. In support of the above arguments, study done by Abbasi and Hollman (2000) tells that when an organization loses a critical employee, there is negative impact on innovation, consistency in providing service to guests may be jeopardized, and major delays in the delivery of services to customers may occur, this may be an alert alarm for the organizations in this highly competitive market. Any retention strategy, practiced or designed in the human resource management discipline, aims to keep talented employees within the organization for mutual benefits for longer tenure.

Theoretical foundation:

In this paper employer branding is consider as cost effective and strategic approach based on general OB/HRD/HRM/Marketing principles to demonstrate the values of the organization with aim to reach best organization-person-fit on basis of people management theory to make the process efficient. Arguments by Kuijpers, et al., (2006) tells that an intrinsic career success is subjectively compared with the person’s own appreciation of his or her career actualization (achievement, future perspectives, recognition, and career satisfaction), whereas extrinsic career success relates to external appreciation (salary and occupational status) is the assumption lying in the interrelationship of internal employer branding and retention of the talented employees, since employer branding principle is supposed to have ability to fulfill the intrinsic career success as

well extrinsic career success because it seems very likely that image perceptions will influence applicants' intentions to pursue employment opportunities at a particular organization (Lemmink et al., 2003) and a strong employer branding can foster feelings of trust and loyalty among existing or future employees (Hays, 2010). It is believed that monetary compensation can influence employees for short-term goals, but cannot sustain a long-term employment relationship because self-achievement is not satisfied (Agarwal & Ferratt, 2001). Present study is advocating to create a brand culture based on deeper people constructs that encourage employee to retain with positive and productive affiliation within the organization which in turn will prove differentiating factor and very important for the organization success, but till date this has been ignored. The underlying concept behind the importance of the internal branding is that employee want to work in a place where they can feel proud of, having larger social acceptance and association identity and have a job that has more than just monetary worth as after associating with the organization employees can garner many things such as economic advantage, fellowship, and social status (Russell, John, Alicia, Grandey & Paul, 1995).

Importance of organizational competitiveness and retaining talent

One of the most significant organizational challenges is high attrition rates which have adverse impact on organizational competitiveness. It means not only loss of talent, but also includes the cost of training the new recruits, organizations have to face the challenge of disruption due to unplanned exits. When the people leave the organization, it demands to relocate the resources like recruitment expenses, training and orientation resources and the time, which further affects the productivity and competitiveness of the organization. Therefore, it is extremely important to deal with this ongoing problem not only for an individual firm but also for the industry as a whole. Globalization, pressure for speed and innovation, and growing competition for talented workers have given organizations added incentives to review their employee relations strategies in order to attract, motivate and retain the workforce that will help them to become successful (Zivnuska, Ketchen, & Snow 2001). Research literature (Axelrod et al, 2001) suggests a shortage of skills in the present decade.

Aligning employer internal branding, organizational competitiveness and talent retention

Employees are the lifeline of any organization and contribute effectively to its successful running and profit making. An organization can't survive if the employees are not serious about it and are more concerned about their personal interests. The internal branding concept is understood as, organizations' internal workforce is the first market of any company to demonstrate their values, benefits and differentiating factors for mutual benefits; the rationale being that employees are internal customers and jobs are internal products (Gronroos C., 2000). Satisfying the overall needs and wants of these internal customers, while focusing the overall objectives of the organization (Rafiq M. & Ahmed P.K., 2000) will offer assured success and competitiveness. Turnover and absenteeism is reduced when employee perceive that their jobs meet their important values (McMurtrey, Grover, Teng, & Lightner, 2002). Ambler and Barrow argued that the focus of the employer brand is "to provide a stable structure for management to simplify and focus priorities, increase productivity and improve recruitment, retention and commitment" (Barrow and Mosley, 2006).

In a recent study done by Pathardikar, Sahu and Maurya (2013) in which the data was collected through incidental sampling from middle level executives of ten organizations in Information Technology (IT) sector in India. Electronic version survey was sent along with a covering letter from the researchers describing the study with the assurance of confidentiality of responses. Four hundred and twenty five questionnaires were mailed. One hundred and fifty surveys were returned, approximately a 35percent response rate. The vast majority (82.7 percent) of the respondents were male. From the mean value of the age the workforce working in the IT organizations are mostly of the young age group with average experience of five years (60 months) and average

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experience in the current organization is about two and half years (30 months). Further findings of this study indicate that employee engagement has positive impact on brand image for communicating the organization being a great place to work. Consequently, employee engagement and employer branding has a substantial impact on employee productivity and this in turn provide competitive advantage. On the other hand employee engagement is another component for the retention of talent (Glen & Clayton, 2006).

Below is the formulated model based on the above findings in support of alignment of employee engagement, employer branding, employee retention and emotional connection in term of loyalty towards brand employer.

Employee retention

As we know that human resources management starts from recruitment to best-fit and finally optimum, effective and efficient utilization of the human capital. This process is based on organization's vision, strategy and human resource planning activities here it comes the role of employer branding i.e. marketing of the organizations vision, mission, culture and work environment to the potential candidate to attract and then after practicing and implementing the people oriented work-practices and providing strength to internal sources such as leadership quality, career/growth opportunity, organizational support, quality of work life and so many others to provide experiential learning and positive feeling among the existing workers that the organization is the suitable place to work, study shows that employer branding creates an emotional connection of brand loyalty with its employees (Pathardikar, Sahu & Maurya, 2013). Based on assumption that "employees who can feel proud of where they work are more likely to remain with that employer" and put their valuable contribution for the mutual benefits internal employer branding is taking wider place in human resources management strategy, because an employment brand can help build that pride and make it easier to communicate to job

candidates that company is a desirable place to work and to build a career .

Conclusion and implications

By sources it has been observed that due to the changing trends, companies are showing interest for deciding separate budget to what has been termed the employee or employer brand, i.e. the set of distinctive associations made by employees (actual or potential) with the employer they work for. As a result this is becoming a better strategy to attract better applicants (Collins & Stevens, 2002; Slaughter et al., 2004) and shapes their expectations about their employment (Lievens & Highhouse, 2003). When critically evaluated, it has been observed that to maintain and increase competitiveness, organizations facing the challenge of retaining their best employees but the recent findings of Pathardikar, Sahu and Maurya (2013) which shows that employer branding is associated with attachment and identification and the end result of identification include support for the organizations, which could be translated as increased commitment to remain within the organization (Mael and Ashforth, 1995) providing an opportunity to organizations for analysis for the internal component of the organizational resources to lead the competition.

Talented workers are important assets of companies, as talent is a source of profit, and sustainable distinctive competitive advantage. Therefore, retaining these workers is becoming the competitive advantage for companies in today's fast-changing environment. It is more critical in Indian industry, because there is a strong demand for positive affiliation of workers in up and downs of the organizations facing due to the uncertainty and continuous changes in Indian market and economy. Although training is an important approach for solving the shortage within the labor force, but development of employee's positive association for longer tenure is important there this is the focus of the research. In terms of future research, more work is needed for integrating the concepts of employer branding. Internal employer branding is a serious effort of the top management for the alignment of organizations workforce with organizations vision, mission and goals to the level of individual's aspiration to work. Therefore human resource managers and top management need to understand the long term effect of these relationships and work on such strategies to overcome the serious problem of attrition and talent management.

Finally employer branding can be defined as "the organizations reputation on the basis of knowledge and experience, benefits in association of the organization which in turn produce the willingness of the stakeholders to continue the industrial relationship with the organization as a „good place to work with". In term of Human resources it can be defined as the ability of the organization to develop the desire in existing and prospective staff that organization is a better place to work for mutual benefit"

Limitation of the study: Base study reported in this paper is limited to one industry in India i.e. IT sector that faces high rate of attrition, therefore more concerned research must be exercised in generalizing our findings to other industries.

Second, while present study tried to link the several internal factors in formulating strategies to overcome the problem of attrition but the limiting to these only may not be helpful since external factors and individual's perception always seems to dominate.

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